

Ethno-Religious Crisis in Northern Nigeria: The Problem of Identity and Inclusion

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Abstract

Ethnicity and religion are still playing vital roles in socio-political existence of Nigeria. Over the years, there are crises and social mishaps that took place under the influence of ethnicity and religion. It is evident that every person in Nigeria is belonging to an ethnic cluster and one of the major religions. Ethno-religious crisis is one of the major threats to peaceful coexistence in Northern-Nigeria which generated instability and insecurity in some States within the region. States like Kaduna, Plateau, Benue, Yobe, Borno, Taraba, Nasarawa, Niger, Kebbi, Bauchi and other States that are pluralistic in nature, suffered series of ethno-religious crises. There are issues facing some of the States with diverse ethnic groups and religions before the amalgamation of the Southern and Northern protectorate, which is still affecting the unity of Nigeria. The 21st century emerged with ethno-religious matters that still remain a national concern. In Nigeria, there are ethnic groups clamouring for exit and quest for a sovereign State. Close to a decade now the Independent People of Biafra (IPOB) and the Oduduwa movement are causing pandemonium across the nation, and gradually drawing global interest. It evident that the face of Politics today in Nigeria is a life two face of coin, known as “Ethnicity and Religion.” This form of identity poses serious threat to the existence of a nationhood. Therefore, this research considers issues facing the unity of the Northern, where there are multi-ethnic clusters and variety of religion, also this paper hinged on primordialist theory which explains amount of power and instruments in communities where there are different religions and ethnic groups.

Keywords: Ethnicity, ethnic identity, religion, nationalism, culture

Introduction

The history and identity of Nigeria is gradually misshaping due to serial issues of national concern which can be traced to ethno-religious matters before the first republic of democratic governance. The Northern Nigeria is one of the sections with complex issues relating to ethnicity and religion before the amalgamation in 1914. The first republic from political stance tried to bring all ethnic groups into political space for the purpose of identification and inclusion of the major and minor ethnic groups, this stride is still a mirage. In view of this, there are ethnic groups within the Northern region who lacked the political will to produce a candidate especially, among the minority kinfolds. The concept of politics over the years in the North was devised and hatched by the Hausa-fulani political class, this movement produced Sir Ahmadu Bello of North West and Sir Tafawa Balewa of North East.

This circle of politics became like a political template for the Northern elites, particularly from the ruling class. This circle of events was seen during the military era, where General Yakubu Gowon from the North-West region became the Head of State during the Civil War 1967-1975, since that experience a Northern Christian never had opportunity to rule the entire Government. This tends to cause serious concern to some ethnic groups that form the minority within the region. There are cases of ethnic groups in the North, since the second republic 1979-1983 were never included in the power sharing which caused some political elites with the region to feel neglected. Racial and religious crises in are now a global concern not only to the Nigeria or Northern region. Ethno-religious crisis in some parts of the Northern-Nigeria can be linked to the history of the formation of regions since the first republic and its enactment by military government. This experience from historical lens, depicts that the Northern region had series of crises which can be described as “ethno-religious” crises, this could relate to Chinua Achebe’s assertion that, “No longer at ease.”¹

Today, there are ethnic clusters, sections of the North and religious groups feeling not identify and included in the share of the commonwealth of the religion. Of recent, there are agitations from Christian political class in the Northern region clamouring for equality in the share of power between the South and the North. The inclusion of the Muslim-Muslim ticket gives signifies there is fairness to the Christian politicians from the North to balance the diversity of Nigeria. Consequently, the Kaduna State Governor, Mal. Nasir El-Rufai set the template of injustice and exclusion of the Southern indigene in 2019 gubernatorial bit. This decision affected the unity of the State and have caused distrust of the intention of the Governor against the Southern-Christian of the State. The northern region in the 21st century is fragmented into ethno-religious sentiments. The Northern Christians and Muslims are no longer living together as it was since, Nigeria became a republic. Therefore, this paper tends to look into the life and crises of some ethnic groups in Northern-Nigeria during pre and post-independence era.

Conceptual Framework

Max Weber, a leading social theorist postulated concepts on “ethnic community action” (*Gemeinschaftshandeln*) as an analytical concept, since it referred to a variety of very different kinds of phenomena.² Weber also held that “primeval phenomena” like ethnicity and nationalism would decrease in importance and eventually vanish as a result of modernisation, industrialisation and individualism.³ Many early to mid-twentieth-century social scientists shared this view. However, it was eventually proven wrong. In fact, ethnicity, nationalism and other forms of identity politics grew in political importance in the world after the Second World War, continuing into the twenty-first century.⁴

From conceptual clarification, Anthropology is a discipline based upon in-depth ethnographic works that deals with wider theoretical issues in the context of particular, local conditions.⁵ Anthropological approaches, moreover, enable us to explore the ways in which ethnic relations are being defined and perceived by people; how people talk and think about their own group and its significant characteristics as well as those of other groups, and how particular worldviews are being maintained, contested and transformed.⁶ Concepts of race can still be appropriate to the extent that they inform people’s engagements; at this level, race exists as a cultural construct, whether it has a biological reality or not. In everyday language the word ‘ethnicity’ still has a ring of ‘minority issues’ and ‘race relations’,⁷ but in social anthropology it simply refers to aspects of relationships between groups which consider themselves, and are regarded by others, as being culturally distinctive. Finally, social anthropology, being a comparative discipline, studies both differences and similarities between distinct inter-ethnic situations and settings.

Should the study of race relations, in this meaning of the word, be distinguished from the study of ethnicity or ethnic relations? Pierre van den Berghe⁸ does not think so, but would rather regard race relations as a special case of ethnicity.⁹ Others, among them like Michael Banton, have argued that, the need to distinguish between ‘race and ethnicity’ is imperative and obvious depending on the context of the people and their worldviews, in real sense what the Western worldview considers race as a major concern in the society, while African considers ‘ethnicity’ as a major concern in the society. In Banton’s view, race refers to the (negative) categorisation of people, while ethnicity has to do with (positive) group identification. He argues that ethnicity is generally more concerned with the identification of ‘us’,¹⁰ while racism is more oriented to the categorisation of ‘them.’¹¹ This would imply that race is a negative term of exclusion, while ethnic identity is a term of positive inclusion. However, ethnicity can assume many forms, and since ethnic ideologies tend to stress common descent among their members, the distinction between race and ethnicity is a problematic one, even if Banton’s distinction between groups and categories can be useful within the context Northern-Nigeria.

Ethnicity is a wider concept than race, as pointed out by Richard Jenkins. Quite clearly, there exist important ethnic differences which are not thought of as ‘racial’ in the sense of being based on group-specific, immutable characteristics.¹² On the other hand, as argued by Peter Wade,¹³ Michel Wieviorka¹⁴ and others, the boundary between what is perceived as natural, biological differences between groups, and acquired, cultural

differences are often uncertain in practice. In view of this concept, this paper tends to look more on ethnicity than race, because what concern the people of the North is ethnic issues knowing fully, they are of the same race. Therefore, there is a need to look at the pitfalls of the first republic in Northern Nigeria, how it was handled by political trailblazers.

Failure from the First Republic in Northern Nigeria

The first republic opened a new democratic tabloid for the people of Nigeria to value ethnic diversity through political process.¹⁵ From conventional point of view, people scope the share of political power was done on the basis of the major ethnic groups both from the North to the South. The President from the South-East (Igbo) and the Prime minister from the North-East (Hausa-Fulani). This concept was initiated for the purpose of balance and inclusion of the Northern and Southern Nigeria depicting colonial legacy. It is evident that the first republic lasted for less than three years, when the military interrupted the republic, the waterloo came as a result of ethno-religious confrontation due political exclusion and power imbalance as perceived by some ethnic groups in the South.

The emergence of the first republic underscored series of political issues that disintegrated both the Northern and the Southern regions. The Hausa-Fulani hegemony has a long history as Larry Diamond puts it, “The Hausa and Fulani are often grouped together because the Fulani, as they conquered the Hausa (first gradually through infiltration over centuries, then decisively in an Islamic holy war (jihad) beginning in 1804), adopted the Hausa language and culture and intermarried with them to such an extent that the two groups have become difficult to distinguish.”¹⁶ In view of this, it is difficult to separate Hausa and Fulani in the North. It is evident that they share the religion and culture together and they are the defenders of the Northern political legacy.

The first republic died prematurely it was due to the problem of identity and inclusion, some of the underlying factors are; the breakdown of constitutionalism by regional political class, federal system formation, regional political instability, and regional domination, abuse of the rule of law by regional political elites and other host of issues which caused the first republic, where some ethnic minorities and the Southern elites felt neglected in the share of the common wealth of the new republic and the body language of the Northern elites seems to show a sign of domination. Consequently, Diamond added that, “A second conventional wisdom of the time was that Nigeria simply fell victim to the centrifugal tendencies inherent in all the multi-ethnic new states of the Third World, and especially in the highly artificial nations clumsily carved for colonial convenience.”¹⁷ This antecedence explains the failure of the elites to intergrade new republic through equal share of power without the use of religion and other political instruments in making other sections of the country to feel neglected or excluded. Diamond further asserts that, “Nothing can be understood about Nigeria until its pattern of ethnic diversity is delineated.”¹⁸

The Northern and the Colonial Legacy

The Northern Nigeria belong to over 300 different ethno-linguistic groups and three major religious groups. In the Northern region, there are few ethnics groups labelled as majority thus are, Hausa, Fulani, Nupe, Tiv, Kanuri, Gbagyi, Jukun, Igala, and others, these ethnic groups cut across the three geo-political zones of the Northern. There are issues and concern in the North that some of the ethnic groups that seems to be majority in the North are excluded in the political process. This poses serious concern in the religion and there are agitations of injustice and neglecting some of the ethnic groups. According to Ugnem, Olutayo, “In 1947, the Tiv in Makurdi rioted in protest of the imposition of *Sarkin* (King of) Makurdi on them. The *Sarkin* Makurdi, Dan Afoda was a Yoruba Muslim who was historically an interpreter for the British Colonialist. At his death in 1947, plans were made for his son to succeed him. This was violently resisted by the Tiv people.”¹⁹

When the British granted Nigeria independence in 1960, they left behind a paradoxical legacy of colonial rule. On the one hand, the Nigerian nation was wholly a colonial construction. The British not only welded these vastly different peoples and regions into a single political entity but left behind the physical infrastructure for

their integration - roads, railway lines, harbours, telephone and telegraph systems, and a common currency.²⁰ But in creating Nigeria, the British also fostered large-scale ethnic consciousness and conflict in the Northern region.²¹ Like other European colonial powers, the British engraved arbitrary and artificial boundaries around their two Nigerian protectorates, merging peoples with few or no common cultural and political bonds and not conscious of religious affiliation.²² Even as leading Nigerian nationalists saw it, 'Nigeria is not a nation. It is a mere geographical expression.'²³ According to the Alhaji Ahmadu Bello, the Premier of Northern Nigeria in his remarks, "the British were the instrument of destiny and were fulfilling the will of God."²⁴ This assertion indicates that the Northern elites adopted the pattern of control over human and natural resources deposited in the Northern region through control and occupation. This impression seems to be to the favour of the Northern political giants and they view it as birth right from the colonial imperialist. The legacy imprinted by the colonialists has affected the state Nigerian unity and peace for the past six decades of existence.

In the words of Turaki, "Colonial legacy refers to colonial philosophy of nation-state building which used racial, ethnic or tribal, religious and cultural values to establish a colonial social order." Consequently, Turaki alludes that "Under colonialism, the Nigerian social environment was nurtured under religious and cultural intolerance, racial inequality and differential and preferential treatment of ethnic groups."²⁵ The Northern political class pattern socio-political life after the pattern of the colonial administrators relegated the minority groups and elevated the majority as the title holders of the Nigerian State. This legacy is gradually affecting the cohesiveness of the nations' diversity. In fact, it was colonial legacy that brought about the down-fall of the first republic in 1966 which brought in the military.²⁶ It is evident that the military adopted the same political tradition of domination over other sections of other regions which was considered as unjust social structures and values of the colonial patriarchs.

The legacy of indirect rule orchestrated by the colonial administration in the Northern region against the minority is still effective in some States where Christians and other ethnic groups are the minority. Therefore, colonial legacy breeds inequality, insecurity and incompatibility, domination and superiority. That is why politics in Nigeria seems to be controlled after independence by the Northern elites. It is evident from mid 1950s to 1965 national politics was dominated by the Northern colonialist and Northern political elites.²⁷ Which makes the Southern elites difficult to have control over the centre. It is evident to note that, the Northern Christian leader who ruled Nigeria as Military Head of State was Gen. Yakubu Gowon from 1967-1975, since such an experience it has been a difficult task for Northern Christians to rule any political office without compromise and betrayal of their people as widely assumed.

According to Turaki. "The institutionalization of States and socio-political role of the Muslim and Non-Muslim groups in the colonial hierarchical structure was an example of stratified inequality and ethnic hierarchy. Crampton states that, "One of the most important events in the history of the North was the Fulani conquest. This came to have lasting effects on its political, social and religious life."²⁸ Fulani ethnic extractions are predominant Muslim, in pre-historic era, the Fulani were nomadic and pastoral people. To the present era, the Fulani people are still maintaining their ancestral heritage both in rural and urban settings through migration. Furthermore, Crampton alludes from historical point of view that, "They began to infiltrate into the North of Nigeria from Thirteenth century, while some intermarried with the Hausa and settled in their town."²⁹

The first republic political parties were formed primarily based on regional and ethnic interests. For example, the Northern People's Congress (NPC) was a dominant party in the Northern Nigeria, which relegated other minorities to form their political party known as "United Middle belt Congress" (UMBC) which created as a regional political identity party for other ethnic groups apart from Hausa-Fulani NPC. The problem of identity and inclusion continued where the minority or the Middle-Belter were not included in the share of the common wealth of the Northern region in the quest for justice, "The Hausa-Fulani NPC dominated government responded by repressing the people. Members of the UMBC were arrested and imprisoned."³⁰ This shows, since the first republic, the issue of ethnic inequality has been on the front burner of Northern politics.

The maiden coup by the Armed Forces which occasioned to counter coups came as a result of ‘perceived’ exclusion and injustice. This affected the state of the nation with distrust among ethno-religious margins. The civil war and post-civil war regimes were equally dominated and controlled by the Northern military leaders. It is obvious that, since 1999 return to democratic governance, the Nation is predominantly controlled by the Northern Political class. According to Alubo, “the politics of inclusion and exclusion in access to resources, resulting from colonial and gene. Politics has resulted in the new identity contests and recreation in contemporary democratic process.”³¹ The quest for socio-political identity in the present democratic regime tends to remind score of ethnic groups of their identity. Since the beginning of independence, the Northern Nigeria has always played the politics of religion and regionalism,³² which in the present democratic era is still having a strong footing. Therefore, ethnicity and religion are the core values of the North.

The Northern Identity

Religion further divided the peoples of Nigeria, but religious cleavage was generally less significant than ethnicity and region. Where religion was a factor in social and political conflict, it typically reflected broader cultural conflict, as in the Middle Belt, which contained 'vigorous concentrations of Christianity among groups of resolute animists.³³ In the East, Islam was virtually absent while Christianity claimed a high proportion of the population, especially among Igbos. Where religion might have functioned to crosscut ethnicity, among the Yoruba - who were fairly evenly split between Christianity and Islam - it failed to do so, because Islam took a different, less encompassing form in the South. As a result, 'Hausa and Yoruba pray at different mosques, and Islam does not function as a crosscutting interethnic solidarity structure³⁴ Within the Northern Region, Islam provided an overarching, trans-ethnic identity throughout the upper North - and hence an important cultural bond for formation of a broader, more modern dominant class - but it also encompassed sectarian cleavage.³⁵ The North is comprised of three geopolitical zones known as North-Central, North-West, and North-East. Each of the zones in the North has variety of cultural and religious identity. The Northern Nigeria as widely assumed by a cluster of people, is controlled by Hausa-Fulani hegemony, this has a tremendous influence in the North.

Hausa language controls almost every segment of the North, the language is used in schools, hospital, market, and other social networks especially in the media outlets. Due to the influence of Hausa language in the North, other ethnic group have no option than to use it for social interaction. This influence places the Hausa-Fulani to feel they are the owners of the North. The fact remains that the Northern region contains different set of cultural and religious expressions that may likely be conflicting based on conviction. This trust is compromised and ignored; it seems there are situations where some ethnic groups within the region feel superior against the minority.

Despite the diversity of the North, there are issues ranging from socio-political to ethno-religious within the region which remain unaddressed since the establishment of the region. This poses serious threat to national existence not regional existence of cluster of ethnic groups in the Northern Nigeria assume the circle of their destiny. According to Castell, “Identity is people’s source of meaning and experience.”³⁶ The Northern Nigeria as widely agreed is segmented into three sections with distinct identity which vary from social life and religion. The point of contention is, if North-Central is part of the Northern region, why excluded in the political process? There are political issues trending on power sharing in some of the political parties especially the People Democratic Party (PDP), where there is an agitation by some party leaders knows as “G5 Governors” from the South and Middle-Belt are calling on the Party Chairman, Ayorchia Ayu to resign for the purpose of equity and justice. The concern from the South is on the Northern domination of the party structure, this clamour is can be considered as identity contest.

The state of insecurity in Northern Nigeria is politicised, ethnocised and religionised by politicians for economic and political reasons. Thus, ethnicity and religion serve as two major forces in advancing crisis in the North. It is true that the Northern region is rich in diversity but the ability to manage and cherish is ignored by the elites. In 2000 Sharia crisis, due to poor management score of people died and properties were destroyed. This

crisis caused a setback to the unity of the Northerners, especially people living in a pluralistic society. Today, in some States in the North there communities predominantly Christians and Muslims in States like Kaduna, Kano, Plateau, Bauchi, Gombe, Yobe, Borno, Kebbi, and others what were affected by serial religious crisis now living between margin. This persistent crisis has created mistrust within the community. "I fear our being controlled by a dictatorial type of government such as can be seen in all the Muslim countries today. We shall all be subject to control by feudal lords who rule by Muslim decree.... This means we shall be ruled by whatever the Koran says."³⁷ The second was the frequent attribution of responsibility for the disunity to the political parties and politicians: "My fear about Nigeria is very great now. I don't know what will be the end of the crisis.... There is no peace all over the country. This is the result of the selfishness of some of our political leaders. [My greatest fear for the country is] disunity among tribes as a result of clamour for power by greedy politicians."³⁸

It is imperative to note that a score of Northerners from political circle owe their allegiance first to their religion and their ethnic origin. This impression shows, loyalty to nationhood comes second. This practice by the Northern political class like the Premier of the region, Sir. Ahmadu Bello poses serious threat to other ethnic minorities from other religions feeling their identity is at stake. The Northern Nigeria with more than 300 different ethno-linguistic group, such as Hausa, Fulani, Kanuri, Nupe, Gbagyi, Tiv, and others. According to Ugben, "in 1947, the Tiv in Makurdi rioted in protest of the imposition of a *Sarkin* Makurdi, Dan Afoda was a Yoruba Muslim who was historically an interpreter for the British Colonialists. At his death in 1947, plans were made for his son to succeed him. This was violently resisted by the Tiv people."³⁹ This manipulation has caused series of ethno-religious crisis in Northern Nigeria.

Causes of the Major Ethno-Religious Crises in Northern-Nigeria

In the analyses of each of the post-Independence crises, there are major crises that have been identified, case by case, are the factors that were most significant in generating the conflict and in producing its unfavourable outcome in the Northern region. Now the underlying pattern across crises must be recognised in the interest of fairness.⁴⁰ By identifying those factors that most consistently and significantly shaped these explosive turns in Nigerian politics, there is a need to consider the failure of the First Republic in handling the ethno-religious tension among the minority in the Northern region who perceived abandoned and excluded in the political process. In view of the causes, there are few that stand out among many in the past decades in the North and are still raising concern in the 21st century democratic era.

a. Demographic Problem

It can hardly be denied that bitter and increasingly polarised ethnic conflict heavily contributed to the fall of the First Republic by the Northern Elites. It was the dominant feature of the census crisis and the 1964 Federal Election, and was more or less dangerously present in every other election contest. It also festered in a number of smaller but still significant incidents, such as the 'ethnic wrangling' following the census, and the University of Lagos crisis. It motivated, at least partially, the 1962 assault on the Action Group (AG), and the subsequent Yoruba feeling of victimisation. Of all the major instances of political conflict, only the General Strike was relatively free of ethnic jealousy, resentment, competition and recriminations. But little is learned by pointing to ethnic antagonism as the cause of political instability.⁴¹ Ethnic conflict was not deeply rooted in Nigerian history; different tribes exchanged goods amicably more often than they warred and, in any case, were less centralised in scale and much less regular in their external contacts. Nor was ethnic antagonism a natural mass phenomenon; most peasants were simply unaware of the vast array of peoples beyond their limited horizons.

From historical perspective, the census or population crisis in the first republic between the North and the South generated a perceived manipulation by the Northern elites for political reasons. The Southern elites thought there was a flaw on the outcome of the result which shows the North has a higher population of people than the South. The emergence of the political system in the Northern region caused mixed reactions among the minority groups, thus Turaki stated that, "Would the Government of the Northern Nigeria dominated by the Muslim groups embark on integrative principles that would better the socio-political role and status of the non-Muslim groups?"⁴²

The Northern Peoples' Congress (NPC) with stronghold in the Northern Region had the power during this period to realise its political interests on almost any issue. The Northern majority in Parliament meant a narrow NPC majority.⁴³ But the margin was too thin for comfort, and NPC leaders no doubt realised even well before the census crisis that in the long run they could not count on their coalition partner, the National Council of Nigeria and the Cameroons (NCNC). Political security, and at least some appearance of political legitimacy and breadth, required a more reliable base of Southern support. This it had obtained by restoring Chief Akintola to power in the West as Atoi puts it,

With the support of his Regional Government and party, the NPC had all the power resources it needed to command the census issue: the Prime Minister, two of the four regional governments, and a solid working majority in Parliament. In this respect, the census crisis was the first tangible demonstration of how much the NPC had gained from the destruction of the Action Group (AG). That the North had the power - i.e., the numbers in parliament - to prevail underscores once again what cannot be stressed too repeatedly: the inherent tension in the federal structure inherited from the British.⁴⁴

The consolidation of the Northern emirates and minorities into a single region with a majority of the Federation's population was probably the most significant and unfortunate legacy of British rule. This bizarre version of federalism biased the political system toward domination by Northern conservatives and so made for a fundamental contradiction between political power, controlled by the North,⁴⁵ and social and economic development, which found the South, quite self-consciously, at a much higher level. In the North what we see in some selected States and communities is the contest of who control the geographical location. The idea of population in the North is considered as a major force and tool for political recognition. In fact, the Northern political elites are proud of their population against the Southern counterpart.

a. Religious Intolerance

The Northern region experiences series of crises as a result of religious intolerance in States that has multi-religious communities. Since the first republic, the North faced different forms of violence connected with religious intolerance. It is evident in Northern Nigeria, religious leaders used intolerable sermons against other religions and other leaders from other faith. The newest form of religious intolerance in Nigeria is the activities of Boko Haram Islamic fundamentalist sect that is currently threatening the co-operate existence of the Nigerian state. This sect has demonstrated high level of intolerance in the country by unleashing terror on both Muslims and non-Muslims alike. According to Onuoha, "the group seeks political and religious reform within the Nigerian state, specifically, the adoption of the Sharia law with beliefs based on the practice of Orthodox Islam."⁴⁶ The sect has been so vocal in questioning the secular arrangement of the Nigerian society in favour of full sharia implementation, and has a very strong hatred for secular education and government establishment.⁴⁷

Evidences abound that insecurity and social instability emanating from intolerance has created so much problems in the Nigerian social space to the extent that it has continued to hinder all efforts channel toward meaningful growth and development in the country's national life. A very good case in point is the Boko Haram enigma, which has continued to overwhelm the Nigerian security agencies since 2009 when it came to the front banner of Nigeria's public sphere.⁴⁸ According to Adesoji, "The outbreak of the Boko Haram uprising in Nigeria in July 2009 marked yet another phase in the recurring pattern that violent uprisings, riots and disturbances have become in Nigeria."⁴⁹ Given the heterogeneous nature of Nigerian society and the religious sensitivity of Nigerians, the situation could perhaps not have been different. But what is alarming is the forceful attempt by Islamic fundamentalists to impose a religious ideology on a constitutionally recognized secular society.⁵⁰

This country has continued to witness endemic destruction of lives and property in contemporary times as a result of religion motivated violence. In this light, one has no option but to ask some pertinent questions: Is the God religious fundamentalists claimed to be fighting for actually the author of peace? If the answer is in the affirmative, why has anarchy and insecurity become colossal in the Nigerian social space in the

name of religion? Why have some followers of religion of peace become so violent to the point that they show very little or no respect for the dignity and sanctity of human life? On the other hand, can it be said that the God of peace has denounced his title and opted for a new title such as the author of violence, and gave his adherents a new mission of causing violence and social unrest in the Nigerian public space? When these poised questions are logically scrutinized, it becomes obvious that something has gone wrong somewhere in matters of religious beliefs and practices in Nigeria and beyond.⁵¹

b. Religious identity, Domination and Exclusion

Nigeria, which will have 200 million people living there by 2019, is the most populous country in Africa. The bulk of scientific and academic sources agree that there are Muslims and Christians in equal numbers. However, as the precise percentages are unknown, several sources provide varying estimates. The figures from various sources are compared in the report's Appendix B of a study conducted by the Pew Research Centre in 2010. For example, the 1963 Census reported that 36% of the population were Christians, 48% were Muslims, and 16% were other.⁵²

However, according to the Demographic and Health Survey from 2008, 53% of respondents identified as Christians, 45% as Muslims, and 2% as other. Similar results were discovered by Afrobarometer in 2008, which indicated 56% Christian, 43% Muslim, and 1% other. Finally, Pew Forum reported in 2009 that 46% of Americans identified as Christians, 52% as Muslims, and 1% as other. Whatever the exact ratios, it is obvious that Nigeria has sizable populations of both Christians and Muslims. Because of this, this nation might serve as a rift between the two identities or perhaps civilizations. This makes Nigeria, which has the biggest proportion of both Christians and Muslims in the world, a "cleft country" and a "test case" for Huntington's Clash of Civilizations theory.⁵³ Christian, Islamic, and traditional religions make up Nigeria's three main religious identities. With "many hundreds of ethnic groupings and sub-groups, villages, clans and kin groups; and, involving the worship of several gods and goddesses," traditional religions are the most politically inactive of the three types. On the other hand, the foundation of religious strife and difference has remained the identities of Christians and Muslims. This distinction is what causes the North-South cleft.

c. Ethnicity and Religion as objects of Manipulation Political Elites

The Northern region today and her politics of ethnicity and religion symbolises manipulation, and especially the ability of elites to simplify and select potent ethnic symbols, remains a high point in any fruitful inquiry of ethnic relations in the North. However, the Northern elite approaches, as they stand now, are incomplete and as such unable to provide a more comprehensive theory of ethnic relations, while contemporary elite theory of ethnicity is epistemologically and conceptually too thin, classical elite theory, which operates with a more structured sociological account of social reality, has little to say about ethnic relations as such. A more nuanced elite theory would have to build upon the epistemological heritage of the classics, aiming on the one hand to overcome their 'naturalism'⁵⁴, determinism and ignorance of ethnicity and, on the other, to provide a more balanced view of culture and politics.

Moreover, a more powerful elite account would also have to offer a broader analysis of ethnic relations that would secure ample treatment of both elite and non-elite action. Although ethnicity is a potent political resource in inter- and intragroup relations, it is a compelling social force precisely because it is more than a political resource. Even in the widespread concern over the disunity in the nation, Free found evidence of a genuine national identity and commitment.⁵⁵ If there were no such identity, he reasoned, Nigeria's internal conflicts would not so frequently have been at the centre of people's hopes and fears.⁵⁶ Among the Nigerian comments on this problem, two themes stand out. First was the Southern fear of Northern domination as the greatest threat to national unity. As things are, it appears Nigeria will be governed all her life by Northerners who were once the most backward people in civilization.⁵⁷ If we allow Northerners to govern us, then in about ten years from now Nigeria will only be regarded as Northern land - and thus all our birth rights sold to the backward set of people.

Conclusion

Ethno-religious conflict is one of the biggest problems the world, and Northern Nigeria in particular, are currently facing. As a developing nation in the twenty-first century, Nigeria's political, economic, and social stability are other challenges that these conflicts have a compounding impact on. A case in point is the ethno-religious struggle in the North, which is multifaceted and extraordinarily complex. In this situation, it is hoped that the modest but useful recommendations presented above may aid in the search for a solution to this urgent issue. This paper attempts to examine the ethno-religious crises that are centred in Northern Nigeria and pose a serious threat to the country's unity among its majority and minority ethnic groups. From an ethno-religious and political standpoint, "identification" and "inclusion" have a social and personal significance to Northern elites who value unity and the advancement of the country. As a result, maintaining our identity in a heterogeneous society must be a joint battle

Recommendations

The makes the following recommendations:

i. True Practice of Federal Character

Governments have the power to establish legal, regulatory, and policy frameworks that encourage racial and religious inclusiveness. The government can make sure that marginalized groups share equally in the benefits of public spending, for instance through social transfers, social protection, and gender/social budget programs. The primary goal of those who support the federal character of the Nigerian polity is to advance the country's sense of oneness. According to Section 14(3) of the 1999 Constitution, "the management of its business shall be carried out in such a manner as to reflect the federal character of Nigeria in the composition of the Government of the Federation or any of its agencies" and the need to foster national cohesion and to inspire national loyalty, preventing a predominance of people from a small number of states or from a small number of ethnic or other sectoral groupings in that government or any of its institutions. Today, it appears that the federal character is only a spirit without a body and is therefore not definable in this world.

ii. Zoning of Leadership positions

In fact, the People's Democratic Party has zoned its presidential ticket to the Northern Nigeria region. There have been several discussions on the efficacy of this practice. Zoning of leadership posts, notably the presidency, is not new to the Nigerian political landscape. But we must keep in mind that zoning will call for alternating leadership, encourage inclusivity and equality among ethnic and religious groups, and do so at both the State and Federal levels. Since the beginning of democracy in 1999, the Eastern Nigerian region has not produced a president; this interest is fiercely kept and will play a role in their alliance and allegiance in the upcoming 2023 elections. Zoning will strengthen Nigerian nationalism and provide the regions a sense of fulfilment and belonging.

iii. Judicious Use of Natural Resources

Natural resources are abundant in Nigeria, particularly natural gas and crude oil. Profits from the sale of oil have supported our economy over the years. However, for Nigerians, the economic results are not very valuable. What happens to the people whose land the resources are obtained? They are not happy to be called Nigerians because they believe that some unidentified people feast on their resources while they are unable to feel the heat of development. The poverty rate has not disappeared, and the irony of plenty still resides with us. National unity will be encouraged when the government uses natural resources wisely and there is an equal distribution of development across the regions.

iv. States Autonomy over Natural Resources

The federal government owns all natural resources that are found on any property, regardless of where it is located. Only the federal government has the independent right to explore and produce these resources. Despite the preceding provisions of this section, Section 44(3) of the 1999 Constitution states that the Government of the Federation shall own the entire property in and control of all minerals, mineral oils, and natural gas found under

or upon any Nigerian land, as well as in, under, or upon the country's territorial waters and Exclusive Economic Zone, and shall manage these resources in any manner the National Assembly may specify. Because the states in Nigeria lack the authority to explore their own natural resources, they are unable to benefit directly and fully from their possession. The states' authority over natural resources will lessen several conflicts that are currently subjects of national concern, leading to national unrest. It is essential to give residents access to a universal system of products and to integrate regions that depend on natural resources. Benue State, for instance, provides the nation with fruits and other agricultural products, whilst the north-western region is responsible for livestock production and supply. The other economic sectors can introduce the similar interplay.

v. Sports/ Youth Activities

Young people have a saying that the only time Nigerians come together is during sporting events. There is some truth in this remark, even though it may not be totally accurate. Sports have the power to unite people, even Nigerians. The Nigerian government, sports associations, and private organizations must support sporting activities that unite the nation's various ethnic communities and regions. A possible solution to the ethno-religious tensions in the North will be the development of national sporting events, celebrations, the introduction of traditional holidays, and even religion. Although it is difficult to alter or adapt ethnic customs, it is essential to try to identify commonalities among different cultures and reassure people that they must make concessions and accept changes in order to preserve Nigeria's unity. In schools, particularly in Northern States, the study of intercultural interaction must be taught. The meeting between youth and representatives of diverse Nigerian cultures is required. They can discuss cultural history, experiences, beliefs, food recipes, traditions, and cultural heritage there. Nothing curbs violence, prejudice, and hatred more effectively than a well-rounded perspective offered by education.

vi. Cultural Integration

Nigeria is a society with diverse culture and people, it is hence difficult to determine what the general culture of the people are, especially in the North. Today, in Nigeria, are languages that enables people from different culture and language to communicate and interact. There is a need to find more common grounds in the cultural symbols and practices of the people in respect to festivals, food, dressing and religion. There is need for religious and traditional leaders in Northern community to encourage followers of the need for intercultural marriage on solve the problems of ethnicity. Intercultural union can be a source of valuing culture and people, in fact, this show respect to people who contributed to the creation of a united Nigerian nation. More inclusive policies can also have broader reaching positive end among religio-cultural groups in Northern Nigeria.

vii. Collaboration of the Civil Society Organizations

Civil society organisations (CSOs) can advocate increased representation and voice for excluded groups in policy and decision-making, and deliver services where the state does not. They can tackle prejudice and change attitudes and behaviour, for instance through the media. The CSOs as Donors have a role to play in supporting national action, ensuring their own programmes take account of advocacy and inclusion among ethno-religious groups in Northern Nigeria. Also, CSOs can assist lesson-learning and dissemination of best practice and hold policy discussions with partner governments, being clear about their values and expectations. They can also support wider alliances for change, innovative pilot approaches and direct service delivery to excluded groups where the State is fragile.

Endnotes

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